

CHARACTERISATION, MODELLING AND PREDICTION OF CRACK GROWTH RESISTANCE IN FIBRE REINFORCED TITANIUM METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper considers the use of fracture mechanics parameters to characterise, model and predict crack growth resistance from unbridged defects in fibre reinforced titanium metal matrix composites subjected to cyclic loading. The conditions under which such parameters are of use, and their experimental measurement are considered. Effects of fibre fracture, stress intensity factor range, mean stress, loading configuration (bending versus tension), and fibre-matrix interfacial strength on fatigue crack growth resistance are highlighted. Finally, a possible approach to prediction of crack arrest in such composites is outlined.

1. INTRODUCTION

At present, there is considerable interest in silicon carbide fibre reinforced titanium metal matrix composites for use in aerospace applications at elevated temperatures. In the longer term, matrix alloys based on titanium aluminides may offer the potential for use at temperature of upto 900°C, but for the present there are attractive lower temperature applications where more conventional titanium alloys are suitable for use as the matrix phase. These composites are expensive to produce and to justify their use it is essential to utilise their mechanical properties fully. Commercially available unidirectionally reinforced materials at ambient temperatures may have longitudinal tensile strengths in excess of 1600 MPa, and they can exhibit fatigue lifetimes of better than 10^4 cycles when stressed at upto 75% of their longitudinal tensile strength.

Under such envisaged loading conditions it is imperative to establish their "fitness for purpose" and reliability. Indeed, to utilise their potential fully it is necessary to develop realistic methods of assessment of damage and validated lifing procedures. It is natural, in view of their envisaged substitution for monolithic alloys in many cases, to consider the use of fracture mechanics parameters including the fracture toughness, stress intensity factor range, and integrated crack growth rates for the prediction of fatigue life. Such parameters are not usually applied to characterise damage in fibre reinforced composites, but it is important to recognise that many studies have established in these titanium MMCs that localised dominant cracks can develop under cyclic loading⁽¹⁻⁶⁾. Examples are shown in Figure 1. Such observations give confidence that a fracture mechanics based approach may be of use provided that effective crack-tip stress intensities can be determined, and such evaluation is the subject of many numerical micromodels⁽⁷⁻¹³⁾. In such models the influence of "bridging length scale" must be considered carefully^(6, 14-16).

The purpose of this paper is to address some of the issues that relate to the characterisation and predictive modelling of crack growth resistance from an initial unbridged defect subjected to cyclic loading. In particular the experimental determination of factors that control crack growth resistance will be considered.

2. EXPERIMENTAL STUDIES

2.1. Materials

Commercially available titanium alloy/silicon carbide fibre composite systems: Ti-15-3/SCS6; Ti-6Al-4V/SCS6; Ti-6Al-4V/SM1240; and Ti- β 215/SCS6 have all been studied. Details of all systems are given elsewhere (3-6, 16-20) but all are reinforced to the same nominal volume fraction of fibres of approximately 0.35. In the metastable β systems ageing treatments have been found to increase the interfacial strength. In most cases unidirectionally reinforced materials only have been considered, but initial tests on cross-ply laminates are now in progress.

2.2. Fatigue crack growth resistance curves

To date, most tests have been confined to single-edged-through thickness notch testpieces in bending, but comparisons for some systems have now been made with single-edged notch testpieces in tension-tension loading. Initial normalised notch depths of between 0.05 and 0.25 have been considered, where the notch depth is normalised to the testpiece width. Crack growth was usually monitored using the direct current potential difference technique. In many cases, care is required to establish appropriate calibration curves of normalised potential to normalised crack depth because of the small size of testpiece under consideration (5).

Tests have usually been performed using a constant cyclic load range, ΔP . Therefore, the nominal applied stress intensity range, ΔK_{app} , increases with increases in fatigue crack length. Crack growth resistance curves can be usefully represented under such testing conditions by plotting crack growth rate per cycle, da/dN , versus either ΔK_{app} or total crack length. Servo-hydraulic testing machines, operating at test frequencies of up to 10Hz, have been used throughout this study. Since these tests require very low loads, the largest load-cell employed was rated to 10kN. Load ratios of both $R=0.5$ and $R=0.1$ (where $R=P_{min}/P_{max}$ and P_{min} , P_{max} are the minimum and maximum loads applied over the fatigue cycle respectively) have been considered.

2.3. In-situ determination of fibre fracture during cyclic loading

Early studies deduced the onset of fibre fracture from audible emissions and rapid voltage excursions observed during crack growth (4, 21). Such events have now been quantified by the in-situ use of both acoustic emission and direct optical observation of the failure of (surface) fibres during cyclic loading. A commercially available PAC LOCAN AE analyser has been used, and under the conditions of use, fibre fracture is characterised by an amplitude of ≥ 90 dB. Details of this system and analysis are given elsewhere (22, 23).

2.4. Evaluation of fibre-matrix interfacial strength

Early studies employed micro-hardness push-out tests, (5, 19) but recently a continuous load-displacement fibre push-out test has been developed at the University of Birmingham. A remote high resolution optical telescope and video recording system have been used to monitor the behaviour of the individual fibres during the push-out tests. Details are given elsewhere, (20) but here it is sufficient to note that such a system allows both the debonding shear stress and the frictional shear stress of the (debonded) interface to be evaluated.

The wide range of assessment techniques employed during these studies have allowed micromechanisms of crack growth in fibre reinforced composites to be elucidated, and they have also highlighted many important factors for controlling crack growth resistance. A selection of some of these results is now presented.

3. GENERAL CHARACTERISATION OF THE FATIGUE CRACK GROWTH RESISTANCE CURVE

In all systems studied to date, crack growth increments per cycle, da/dN , decrease initially with crack length increase ahead of the initial unbridged defect, examples are given in Figures 2 and 3. Such decreases in crack growth rates are despite an increase in nominal applied stress intensity range, ΔK_{app} , with crack length increase. An explanation for this unusual crack growth behaviour is given by considering optical sections through interrupted fatigue crack growth tests, see Figure 1. The micromechanism of crack growth is well characterised by initial crack growth through the matrix which breaches (debonds) fibres and leaves them intact and bridging the crack in its wake. (In studies to date no fibres have been observed to fail ahead of the growing fatigue crack tip). The bridging fibres then reduce the effective stress intensity at the growing crack tip, ΔK_{eff} , and if no (or very few) fibres fail then crack growth rates decrease eventually to crack arrest defined here by $da/dN \leq 10^{-8}$ mm/cycle. The balance between sub-critical crack growth and catastrophic failure will be governed primarily by the number of fibres remaining intact within the crack wake, see Figure 1 and Table 1.

A second general feature of all tests to date is that the failure of discrete fibres often sharply increases local crack growth rates, see Figure 3, where the failure of fibres has been identified unequivocally by acoustic emission techniques. (For reference a complete amplitude distribution for events detected during this test is given in Figure 4). Note to measure such local increases in crack growth rate it is essential to monitor crack growth rates by continuous potential difference techniques. These observations indicate that to model these systems the fibres must be considered as discrete entities⁽¹¹⁻¹³⁾. Moreover, many tests have illustrated that fibres may fail after extended cycling in near crack arrest regions, and which may plausibly be interpreted as a result of changes to fibre-matrix interfacial regions with cycling.

The paper now considers some specific experimental observations which indicate controlling features of these composite systems when subjected to cyclic loading in the presence of a through-thickness unbridged defect.

3.1. Effects of fibre-matrix interfacial strength

After peak ageing the interfacial strength of the $\beta 21S/SCS6$ composite system increases significantly, compared with solution-treated or as-processed conditions. Values of the debonding shear stress increase from approximately 80 to 120MPa, and values of the frictional shear stress (after debonding) increase from 100 to 180 MPa. Moreover, the number of cycles to failure decreases sharply from a minimum of 1,800,000 for as-processed and solution treated conditions to 88,000 for the peak aged condition. These studies are reported elsewhere,⁽²⁰⁾ but here it is noted that the initial stress intensity factor range was sufficient to promote fibre failure in all conditions. Under these circumstances an increase in interfacial strength would be expected to increase the incidence of fibre failure and hence to promote earlier catastrophic failure, because the fibres will be more highly stressed as a result of more efficient load transfer.

3.2. Effects of loading geometry

Figure 2 suggests that crack arrest can occur more readily under tensile loading than under three point bending, for tests performed under identical initial ΔK_{app} conditions. However, this can be shown to be a function primarily of the rate of increase in stress intensity range with crack increment by matching the rate of nominal ΔK_{app} increase for each geometry. (This is achieved simply by load range shedding for the tensile geometry and load range increases for the bending geometry after appropriate crack depth increments).

Under such conditions, similar crack growth behaviour can be produced for each testpiece geometry, and this illustrates the usefulness of even nominal stress intensity parameters in characterising crack growth *in similar testpieces* (24).

3.3. Effects of mean stress and initial applied stress intensity range

Major effects of such parameters are seen when higher levels of mean stress and/or higher levels of initial applied stress intensity range promote increased incidences of fibre failure. Under such conditions they can promote catastrophic failure rather than crack arrest (4-17). Recently, systematic studies considering both these factors have resulted in a simple model for the prediction of fibre failure for testpieces of a specific geometry and for a given composite system (Ti-6Al-4V/SM1240). This is reported elsewhere in more detail (16), but some of the results are also summarised in Table 2. Since crack arrest occurs if few fibres fail, then if K_{max} values (where K_{max} is the maximum nominal stress intensity factor applied over the fatigue cycle) after the first row of breached fibres are kept below 27.5 MPam^{1/2} then crack arrest will be predicted, and is consistent with the experimental observations in this single system. It is of interest to note that such values of K_{max} that can be tolerated vary with composite system for testpieces of identical geometry, and are greatly reduced for a 0/90 cross-ply laminae (which has only half the number of 0° bridging fibres present for an equivalent increment of crack depth), see Table 3.

4. GENERAL DISCUSSION

Several factors that may control crack growth resistance have been demonstrated experimentally. Although no unique relationship between an applied nominal stress intensity factor range and crack growth rate can be defined, it is hoped that the use of parameters such as ΔK_{app} and K_{max} to characterise crack growth resistance for specific testpiece geometrics has been illustrated. Moreover, the beginning of a predictive model to address crack arrest has been outlined. It considers the failure of fibres to be controlled primarily by the level of K_{max} applied after they have been breached by matrix crack growth (a quantitative description will require local crack opening displacements under load and detailed numerical micromodelling), and the extent of fibre failure determines the integrity of the composite.

The degree of complexity inherent to crack growth resistance in these materials should not be underestimated. Effects of interfacial strength, mean stress, testpiece geometry and initial applied stress intensity factor range or crack growth resistance under cyclic loading will always be significant if they alter the balance of the number of bridging fibres that fail for any given crack depth increment. Great care is needed if fracture mechanics concepts are to be applied to the reliability of components containing a range of crack shapes and sizes, and the approach will require both predictive modelling and experimental validation.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Dominant localised fatigue cracks are produced from unbridged defects in fibre reinforced titanium alloy composites subjected to cyclic loading. The growth of these cracks can be characterised by the use of fracture mechanics parameters. Crack growth resistance is controlled by the number of intact fibres bridging behind the growing fatigue crack-tip in its wake. Effects of interfacial strength, applied stress intensity factor range, mean stress and testpiece geometry on crack growth resistance will be marked if the balance of the number of bridging fibres that fail for a given increment of matrix crack growth is altered. For specific testpiece geometrics and fibre architecture, the onset of fibre failure appears to be controlled by the maximum nominal stress intensity factor applied over the fatigue cycle.

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Number of Bridging Fibres Remaining Intact	K_{max} (nominal) (MPa \sqrt{m})	Type of Event
8	39	Catastrophic Failure
12	64	Catastrophic Failure
26	66	No Growth
21	80	No Growth
16	51	No Growth
7	64	Catastrophic Failure

Table 1. The importance of the number of bridging fibres intact in the crack wake on stable/unstable crack growth transitions.

Stress Ratio	initial ΔK (MPa \sqrt{m})	initial K_{max} (MPa \sqrt{m})	K_{max} after 1st row fibres (MPa \sqrt{m})	Test Result
0.5	12.1	24.2	25.8	Crack Arrest
0.5	13.8	27.6	29.8	Catastrophic Failure
0.1	22.3	24.8	27.5	Crack Arrest
0.1	25.0	27.8	30.2	Catastrophic Failure

Table 2. Effects of mean stress; initial ΔK_{app} , K_{max} ; K_{max} after the first row of fibres; on crack growth resistance.

Material	K_{max} after first row of fibres (MPa $m^{1/2}$)	Test Result
Ti-6Al-4V/SCS6	22.5 28.8	Crack arrest Catastrophic failure
Ti- β 21S/SCS6	39.6 40.6 45.6	Crack arrest Catastrophic failure Catastrophic failure
Ti-15-3/SCS6	35.0 42.2	Crack arrest Catastrophic failure
Ti-6Al-4V/SCS6 (0/90 laminate)	15.0 19.8	Crack arrest Catastrophic failure

Table 3. Comparison of experimental observations of crack growth behaviour related to K_{max} after the first row of breached fibres.

Figure 1. Optical micrographs of sections through interrupted fatigue crack growth: (a) Ti-6Al-4V/SCS6; (b) Ti-15-3/SCS6;

Figure 2. Crack growth resistance curves: da/dN versus total crack length for initial $\Delta K_{app} \cong 17\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}^{1/2}$, $R=0.5$, $\nu=10\text{Hz}$. Ti-15-3/SCS6 composite, solution treated, and tested at ambient temperature under cyclic bending and cyclic-tension.

Figure 3. Crack growth resistance curve: da/dN versus nominal ΔK_{app} for initial $\Delta K_{app} \cong 18 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}^{1/2}$, $R=0.1$, $\nu=0.5\text{Hz}$. Ti-6Al-4V/SCS6 0/90 cross-ply laminate, tested at ambient temperature. Individual fibre failures measured using AE events are arrowed.

Figure 4. Acoustic emission amplitude spectrum measured after failure for the 0/90 cross-ply laminate.